

Data Collections Of National Significance

DataRetention@ARDC

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Preamble

Research data collections are the logical arrangements of research data generated as part of the research process; they present as evidence supporting scholarly communication. It follows that research data collections are important and valuable consequences of research and the evidence that underpin the scholarly record and a national Digital Research Infrastructure. In the same way that ideas are built upon via scholarly communication, data collections can be reused for further and future research. Where once libraries were established to house collections of scholarly communication, data collections are presented to sector stakeholders via digital infrastructures, primarily storage and access services. While conventional libraries require physical facilities and people, so do digital infrastructures, irrespective of whether these infrastructures are managed directly on premise, indirectly through third party services, or virtually via cloud services.

We call these research collections ‘Data Collections of National Significance’.

To better understand the operational dynamics of significant data collections, this reference definition document was constructed to describe conditions of significance (why data should be retained) and in doing so enable a classification of data collections that could inform sustainable infrastructure investment. In the first instance this document only concerns research data collections in academic context. We acknowledge that additional collections of high research value exist outside the current scope, for example government departments and agencies, and that future consideration of those data collections will enrich this reference document and provide a more inclusive perspective.

Background

Until recently, managing data storage infrastructures has benefited from technology advances in data capacity density and rapidly decreasing hardware costs. A strategy that to date has shielded storage facilities from the accelerating data growth rates. This is no longer the case¹ and it appears inevitable that consideration be made to define and implement constraints/gates on what data to store, where and for how long.

Traditional publication evolved a constraint framework to select valuable records of research over unsupported assertions; these constraints took the form of peer-review and became a foundational constraint mechanism for academic publishing and research funding; value in scholarly communication is managed by academic publishers and academic funders. There is no such value framework for research data despite years of investment in data management practice and considerable support for national data storage capacity.

Much like for scholarly communication, the familiar academic conventions of peer review (for publications) and strategic investment (grant authorities) can also be employed to make important judgments on research data collections.

¹ Data storage hardware costs are no longer falling faster than data growth see <<https://jcmmit.net/mem2015.htm>>

Example 1: Traditional publication. The publication of a journal article imparts sufficient value for that output to be recognised as valuable and preserved for future reference.

Example 2: Formal research funding: Not all data collected is used for an academic publication and many research grants produce data whose evidential value is poorly recognised, like null results that fail to disprove hypotheses.

Example 3: Strategic investment: The Australian government established NCRIS as a strategic investment into the national research sector. The facilities and capabilities provide significant strategic value to the sector and can be well represented by the data they generate, either as a service or via participating researchers.

In all examples, the research data collected represent significant research assets but current practice often manages them as historical artefacts; unavailable, un-reusable, poorly attributed and at significant risk of loss.

Characterising infrastructure challenges as they relate to significant research data collections is critical to future strategic investment but also maximises the impact of already acquitted investment.

Motivation:

Data require infrastructure to exist. As bit volume and/or collection number increase, the burden of managing these infrastructures shifts from a process characterised by content standardisation and policy to one characterised by macro-scale service management strategies of automation and migration.

Common to both infrastructure management characteristics is the need to establish a value to data, accommodate an often specialised pathway from creation to disposal and a facility management capability that can provide the most cost effective storage environment options, for the correct amount of time and accessible to the most appropriate stakeholders.

Problem Statement:

An accurate and predictable growth profile for data and infrastructure is complex and reliable details are largely absent. Agreed measures of value (of research data) and purpose (of data infrastructures) are unrecognised or poorly articulated. Further, it is self-evident that all research data collections are NOT of equal value but that no consistent value framework exists to instantiate these inequalities.

Together this makes designing an effective inclusive national investment strategy near impossible.

The ARDC Data Retention Project sought to construct a definition for data collections of national significance and articulate any consequences of such a designation as a necessary precondition to designing a realistic and sustainable and strategic investment framework. Our definition makes use of the existing framework of meritorious grant allocation, strategic investment and citation in scholarly

communication and applies them to data collections as formal outputs from the research endeavour. The outcome is a foundational and consistent measure of value and practice captured in an international metadata schema that describes research conventions (as well as industry practices) associated with traditional academic impact.

Data Collections of National Significance

A research data collection is considered significant if its value can be validated against a substantive independent review process, either as part of the traditional scholarly record (either output or input), result of formal grant funding decisions, or as a consequence of national strategic investment (generated or stored for use by Australian researchers).

Data collections are measured as significant if they can be classified important or valuable according to the following:

- A data collection is considered **important** if it was generated as output from a formal competitive grant funding process or framework, e.g. ARC/NHMRC funding bodies OR been generated², or managed by³ a national strategic investment like an NCRIS facility.
 - ◆ The Data Retention Project describes important data collections with 8 metadata elements relating to individuals, organisations, capacity textual narrative, grant codes, discipline codes and persistent identifiers.

- A data collection is considered **valuable** if it has been formally recorded in the scholarly record as a citation within a peer reviewed or edited publication or has been managed post-project, to the FAIR data principles.
 - ◆ The Data Retention Project describes valuable data collections with 13 metadata elements, relating to individuals, organisations, capacity textual narrative, grant codes, discipline codes, citations, publications, licences and persistent identifiers

Data that do not fulfil at least one of the above may have unrealised value or no value and should be supported as a locally responsibility until such time as their significance can be realised and documented.

Once classified, data collections should be supported on the most cost-effective renewable investment until they become dormant and are either deleted, destroyed or placed into archive/cold storage.

² For example as an output from a national instrument facility

³ For example if a large data collection (national or international) is maintained for the benefit of Australian researchers as a local copy.

Data collections that are regularly reused or are persistently recorded in the scholarly record via citation in a peer reviewed or edited publication, increase in value.

Consequences:

If a data collection is considered a data collection of national significance it is expected to establish and maintain as FAIR a state as possible, relative to its lifecycle. Such collections require non-trivial infrastructure considerations that include:

- Capacity and version management,
- Resilience concerns of latency, redundancy and disaster recovery,
- Dissemination, access, acknowledgement and appropriate governance,
- Defined periods relating to the above (time accessible, restoration latency, citation tracking)

Universities and NCRIS capabilities are more likely to attract support from the ARDC and others if they manage data collections leading to, or in the context of a national corpus of significant data collections, considered FAIR in line with established academic conventions.

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